

Speculation on the Relativistic Association of E,p with Spacetime and Quantum Mechanics

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In previous notes, we argued that quantum and classical features coexist in free particle quantum mechanics because $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (probability for an interaction at t or x) follows from $-Et+px$, but $x=vt$ is a deterministic equation that applies to the center-of-mass motion. In other words, interactions involve stochasticity. One might argue that this entire notion follows from the use of $-Et+px$ (Lorentz invariant). If one did not use this invariant, one might argue that an association between E,p and x,t might not exist. Here we argue to the contrary.

While Newtonian mechanics uses $KE = p^2/2m$ so that v does not need to appear explicitly if one uses $E=KE$ and p , such is not the case in special relativity. There, one has E and p and might argue that physically these are variables linked with an interaction. At first, v does not appear explicitly if one simply writes E and p , but it does appear if one divides p/E for a particle with rest mass. Now v is directly linked to the deterministic $x=vt$ (for $x_0=0, t_0=0$) and so we argue that spacetime is inherently present if one links E to p . For a photon, $E=pc$ and $c=x/t$ and so one cannot escape linking E,p with spacetime as well. Given that E and p are measures in E,p space, we suggest that there must be corresponding measures in x,t space (i.e. $\hbar/p, \hbar/E$).

Moreover, we suggest that there might be two kinds of information present. It is well-known that $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ (i.e. resolutions), but given that $p = E/c$ or v one might consider two particles with the same p , one with v_0 , the other with $2v_0$. Then quantum time resolution information is $(T/(\hbar/E))$, while for a fixed x , $2v_0$ only experiences half the time (half a different kind of time information) or deterministic time information is proportional to $1/v$. The ratio of the two is constant for p constant. For $E=p/v$ ($c=1$), one may have two particles with the same E , but $v_0, 2v_0$ (and hence $p_0, 2p_0$). Quantum spatial resolution information is $L/(\hbar/p)$ while for a fixed time $2v_0$ sees twice the space, i.e. twice the information. Again, the ratio of the two types of information is a constant.

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics arises from the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px \quad (1)$$

If one has a given t,x (presumably $x=vt$), then there exists another set:

$$t_1=t + \hbar/E \text{ and } x_1=x+\hbar/p \quad (2) \text{ such that } -Et+px \text{ remains unchanged.}$$

We have suggested that this means there is uncertainty in the time and position at which an interaction occurs. We further suggest that t and x are independent, but their possible ranges are linked by $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ such that $-Et+px$ remains constant. This leads

to the notion of a complex probability which has two features. First, it creates periodic resolution units in time and space and secondly, when multiplied by its complex conjugate, it yields 1 which means that an interaction may occur at any x or t with the same probability.

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) = \text{probability} \quad ((3))$$

All of these ideas seem to follow directly from $-Et+px$. If one did not know about this Lorentz invariant, one might argue that E and p are not linked with spacetime (x,t) and one would not consider special relativity as being associated with free particle quantum mechanics. We try to argue that this is not the case.

Inherent Link Between E,p and Spacetime through v in Special Relativity

In Newtonian mechanics:

$$KE = p^2/2m_0 \quad \text{and} \quad p = mv_0 \quad ((4))$$

Even though v appears in $p = mv_0$, p is linked physically with an impulse hit so that $p = mv_0$ and $2m_0 \cdot 0.5v_0$, yield the same impulse, KE and p are linked through ((4)) and v does not appear explicitly.

Such is not the case in special relativity. Even if one had no knowledge of the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, one has:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = mv_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((5))$$

One may see that unlike Newtonian mechanics:

$$p = E/c \cdot v \quad \text{for a particle with rest mass} \quad ((6))$$

As a result, for a particle with rest mass, one cannot think only in terms of E and p without v present, because the ratio of p/E is proportional to v . v is linked with the deterministic equation

$$x = vt \quad ((7))$$

and explicitly contains spacetime (x,t) . Thus, we argue that one has no choice to associate spacetime with E and p for a particle with rest mass. In the case of a photon, one has:

$$E = pc \quad \text{where } c \text{ is the speed of the photon which is associated with } x = ct \text{ and} \quad ((8))$$

and so spacetime is present as well. As a result, one cannot treat the interaction variables E,p as being independent from spacetime. A change in E and p must be linked to some kind of change in space time. We try to look at this change from an information point of view.

Two Kinds of Spacetime Information and E,p

It is well-known in Newtonian mechanics, that two particles with different m_0, v values, but the same p yield the same impulse. In special relativity:

$$p = E/c * v \quad ((9))$$

If one considers that $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and that these resolutions represent information, one may try to think of ((9)) in terms of information.

For a period of time T , then $T / (\hbar/E) =$ amount of information seen

For a length L , then $L / (\hbar/p) =$ amount of information seen ((10))

The above information is linked with quantum resolution. ((9)), however, also contains v . We suggest that v might be linked with a different kind of information. Given that E is linked with time, we consider the same length and argue that $2v$ only experience half the time, i.e half the time information as v . Then the ratio of the two kinds of information is constant.

P as information proportional to $T / (1/E) / 1/v$ ((11))

If $E=2E_0$ and $v= v_0 .5$, then ((11)) shows that the ratio of these two kinds of information remains constant. If two p 's (consisting of E_0, v_0 and $2E_0, .5v_0$) have the same information and are equivalent.

For the spatial scenario, $E = p/v$. If one has two particles with the same E , ($c=1$), then for $v=2v_0$, $p=2p_0$ one again takes the ratio of the two informations. In this case, $2v$ represents double the x information, because a particle travels twice as far in a given t as for v .

E information proportional to $L/(\hbar/p) / v$ ((12))

Thus, length information is proportional to v . Again ((12)) shows that the two particles with the same E have the same information (quotient of two different kinds of information).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even if one does not consider the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ when trying to argue for a free particle quantum mechanics based on $\Delta x = \hbar/p$, $\Delta t = \hbar/E$, one must acknowledge that for a particle with rest mass, $p = E/c * v$. In special relativity In Newtonian mechanics, $KE = p^2/2m$ and so v does not appear explicitly, but is present in the former expression, meaning, we argue, that one cannot escape a relationship between E, p and spacetime through $v=x/t$. For a photon, $E = pc$ and $c=x/t$ for the photon, so again there is a spacetime link. We further suggest that one might try to think in terms of two kinds of information for a particle with rest mass. $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ which are resolution

information, i.e. $T/(\hbar/E) =$ time resolution information and $L/(\hbar/p) =$ space resolution information. Given $p = E/c * v$, we suggest that E is linked with time information and so there might be another kind of time information linked with v . If x is constant, then for v_0 and $2v_0$, $2v_0$ experiences half the time, i.e half the deterministic time information. Then, for two particles with the same p , but v_0 and $2v_0$, one has: p information proportional to $T/(\hbar/E) / 1/v$. This means that the two particles with the same p have the same product of two different kinds of information, one quantum (resolution) and the other classical (linked to $x=vt$). The same argument may be made for $E=p/v$ ($c=1$). One again uses a ratio of the two kinds of information.